

PREVALANCE OF HYPERPROLACTINEMIA AND THYROID DISORDERS AMONG PATIENT WITH ABNORMAL UTEIRENE BLEEDING (AUB)

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Abstract: Background: Abnormal uterine bleeding is defined as a state of abnormal uterine bleeding without any clinically detectable organic pelvic pathology-tumour, inflammation or pregnancy. The International Federation of Gynecology and Obstetrics (FIGO) defines chronic abnormal uterine bleeding (AUB) as “bleeding from the uterine corpus that is abnormal in duration, volume, and/or frequency and has been present for the majority of the last 6 months.

Aim of study: To evaluate the prevalence of hyperprolactinemia and thyroid disorders among patients with abnormal uterine bleeding (AUB).

Patient and methods: Observational Commprehesive study was done at gynecological department of Immamain Al Khadmain teaching hospital in Baghdad The study was carried out for a from 1stNovember 2020 to the 31 of october2021. (50) patients with complaints of abnormal uterine bleeding(group A) and who attended to Gynecology clinic at Al-Immamain Al- Khademaian teaching hospital for treatment or follow up and matching with another(50) patients with regular or normal menstrual cycle(group B) and selected according to specific criteria that included in this study.

Result: the result for group (a) was as the following ,according to age group the most prevalent age were (40-45)36%;the most prevelant bleeding pattern was mennorrhia(40%);among the female with para3(26%); The result according to hypothyroidism and hyperprolactinemia were for patient with high TSH(54%) and (58%) respectively.

Conclusion:

From our study it is evident that thyroid disorder and hyperprolactinemia is associated with abnormal uterine bleeding in a significant number of patients.

Keywords: Abnormal Uterine Bleeding (AUB), Hyperprolactinemia, Thyroid Disorders, Hypothyroidism, Menorrhagia, Gynecology, Hormonal Imbalance, Reproductive Health, Chronic AUB, FIGO Criteria.

Introduction

Menorrhagia, which is defined as regular bleeding from the uterus that occurs more than eight times per cycle, or irregular anovulatory bleeding, which is defined as bleeding episodes that occur outside of the menstrual cycle, which produces a significant complaint and/or concern on the part of the patient without the presence of clinically recognizable uterine pathology, such as tumors, inflammation, or pregnancy [1]. AUB is a common and the majority of the time symptomatic gynecological condition. Aub is characterized from other types of bleeding by the qualitative changes that occur over the course of bleeding, which are determined by the amount of blood that is lost and the frequency of bleeding. adrenocorticotropic uterine

hyperplasia (AUB), also known as the hypothalamus-pituitary-ovarian-MRI axis, is the origin of the majority of instances. In this particular instance, the aforementioned condition is the reason. The hormonal imbalances that are frequent throughout the ovarian years, including the adolescent and perimenopausal periods, may be affected by these interruptions, which may have an effect on the hormonal balance. AUB is quite common in women of these ages because these disruptions may induce alterations in the endometrium, which is the reason why it is so common. According to the International Federation of Obstetricians and Gynecologists (FIGO), chronic bleeding of the uterus (AUB) is defined as "uterine corpus... hemorrhage [that is] of abnormally duration, volume, and/or frequency which has occurred for the considerable majority of the last six months" [2]. HMB, also known as menorrhagia or dysfunctional uterine bleeding, is characterized by persistent bleeding. This type of bleeding can have detrimental effects on a woman's quality of life, resulting in major health risks in severe cases and, consequently, referrals for hysterectomy [3]. Because of this, the implications of HMB can be severe. This is especially true in situations when there is a significant amount of bleeding. There are numerous subtypes of menorrhagia, which include the following: menorrhagia is characterized by heavy bleeding during one period and several subsequent cycles. The physical, emotional, and social components of a woman's life are all impacted by this syndrome [3]. AUB has been linked to a number of menstrual irregularities, some of which include the following occurrences: It encompasses menorrhagia, which is characterized by normal intervals coupled with strong flow or a protracted period that exceeds seven days. Polymenorrhea is defined as bleeding intervals that are less than 21 days, whereas oligomenorrhea is defined as bleeding intervals that are more than 35 days. Menometrorrhagia is defined as irregular non-cyclic intervals, high flow, or extended bleeding [4]. The so-called regularity, which can be classified as regular, irregular, or absent; the length of the flow, which can be classified as prolonged, normal, or shorter; the frequency, which can be classified as frequent, normal, or uncommon; and the volume, which can be classified as heavy, normal, or light; language has been simplified in such a way as to improve the capacity for diagnosis and treatment [2]. Two phrases that are used to make reference to a condition in which the quantity of blood that is lost during the menstrual period is thought to be excessive are "heavy menstrual bleeding" and menorrhagia. Some individuals may be able to utilize these terms since they are two terms that are used to describe the issue. Therefore, it is essential to have a thorough comprehension of both ovulatory and anovulatory hemorrhage [4]. The therapy of atypical uterine bleeding is contingent upon the etiology, and there is a distinct distinction between the two types of bleeding. As a result of the fact that AUB encompasses a wide range of illnesses that are characterized by a multitude of symptoms that are interconnected, and that these diseases often have distinct etiological origins, it is essential to do differential diagnosis and to personalize treatment to each individual patient. Due to the fact that it has an impact on the general health of women, it is essential that daily research and medical inspection be conducted in order to acquire an understanding of the new methods of diagnosis and to enhance the treatment process [4]. This study aim To evaluate the prevalence of hyperprolactinemia and thyroid disorders among patients with abnormal uterine bleeding (AUB).

PATIENT AND METHODS

Design and setting

Observational Comprehensive study was done at gynecological department of immamain al khadmain teaching hospital in Baghdad city. The study was carried out for a from 1st November 2020 to the 31 of October 2021.

Study population:

Target population in this study were total (100), (50) patients with complaints of abnormal uterine bleeding (group A) and who attended to Gynecology clinic at Al-Immamain Al- Khademaian teaching hospital for treatment or follow up and matching with another (50) patients with regular or normal menstrual cycle (group B) and selected according to specific criteria that included in this study.

Selection criteria:

1. Inclusion criteria:

- Patient aged were from 20 to 45 years old.
- Parity(nill para,para1,2,3,4,5)
- Accept to participate in study.
- Ultrasound showing normal uterus and adnexa and no organic lesion seen.
- Women with any of the following menstrual disturbances (A cyclical bleeding, Menorrhagia, Metrorrhagia, Oligomenorrhoea, Hypomenorrhoea, Polymenorrhoea, Polymenorrhagia).

2. Exclusion criteria:

- Patients age below 20 years and above 45 years.
- Diagnosed case of organic lesion by pelvic examination and by US (ovarian cyst, uterine fibroid, polyp adenomyosis, endometriosis and malignant tumors (endometrial and cervical).
- Patients with carcinoma of thyroid.
- Patients who are on drugs (warfarin) or hormones treatment) and patient taking chemotherapy, medication affecting platelets functions and IUCD users.
- Patients with history of bleeding disorders such as (haemophilia, von Willebrand's disease).
- Pelvic infections including endometritis
- Patients with diabetes mellitus, hypertension and cardiovascular disease.
- Patients who smoking.
- Patients with autoimmune diseases, rheumatoid arthritis and inflammatory bowel disease.

Study procedure:

1. Questionnaire: -

- The demographic information includes, age, parity, and duration of disease, past menstrual history(onset ,duration)and drug history .
- Disease information including: patient complain, duration, family history, past medical history (thyroid disease, anemia, etc) and past drug history.

2. Physical examination:

General exam (look for the sign of anemia such as pallor and tachycardia with examination of sclera and patechia with bruises

- And abdominal examination by palpation (any pelvic mass)
- And gynecological exam by (abdominal or tranvaginal US)
- And per vaginal exam,
- To exclude infections and any organic lesion (such ovarian lesion, uteriene lesion, etc).

3. Laboratory investigation:

- Basic routine investigations like **CBC**, urine.
- T3,T4 and TSH
- S. prolactin.
- Bleeding profile to exclude cases of bleeding tendency

Statistical Analysis:

Data was translated into a computerized database structure. Statistical analyses was done using SPSS (Statistical Package for Social Sciences). Version 20 computer software for windows. Categorical variables were presented as frequency and percentage, Chi-square was used to test the significance of the association between categorical variables, Data were presented as mean, standard deviation and ranges. Two-sample t-test was used for comparison between variables. With considered P. Value of ≤ 0.05 was statistically significant.

RESULTS

The total sample of current study included 100 patients, out of them 50 patients with abnormal uterine bleeding (group A) and 50 patients without abnormal uterine bleeding (group B), the mean age of study sample were (32.06 ± 5.382), the most prevalent age category were (35-40 years) 26%. While the most prevalent age category among group A were (40-45 years) 36% with statically significant association between age and study groups ($p=0.021$). regarding to BMI of study sample the result found 48% were normal BMI and 22% were obese, in group A we see more obese patients than control group (24% and 20% respectively) but without statically significant association ($p=0.854$). as shown in table 1.

Regarding to distribution of study sample according to parity, the result of study found the highest present were among para 3(23 %) most of them where among group A than group B (26 % and 20% respectively) and we see the number of patients more among group A in parity 4 and 5 while among group B were decrease with increase of parity with statically significant association ($p=0.043$). another hand the result of study found 90% of group A were married and 84% among group B without statically differences ($p=0.277$). as shown in table 1.

The result of current study showed most prevalent types of bleeding pattern among group A were menorrhagia (44%), follow it polymenorrhagia (22%) and after that coming metrorrhagia (18%) and finally oligomenorrhoea (16%).As shown in figure(1)

Table 1: distribution of study sample according sociodemographic characteristic.

AGE	Group A	Group B	Total	P value
20-25 years	4 (8.00%)	6 (12.00%)	10 (10.00%)	0.021*
25-30 years	8 (16.00%)	13 (26.00%)	21 (21.00%)	
30-35 years	9(18.00%)	12 (24.00%)	21 (21.00%)	
35-40 years	11 (22.00%)	15 (30.00%)	26 (26.00%)	
40-45 years	18 (36.00%)	4 (8.00%)	22 (22.00%)	
total	50 (100.00%)	50 (100.00%)	100 (100.00%)	
Pearson Chi-Square= 11.514a df= 4 statically significant *				
BMI	group A	group B	Total	P value
Normal 18.5-24.9 kg	24 (48.00%)	24 (48.00%)	48 (48.00%)	0.854
Over weight 25- 29 kg	14 (28.00%)	16 (32.00%)	30 (30.00%)	
Obese ≥ 30 kg	12 (24.00%)	10 (20.00%)	22 (22.00%)	

total	50 (100.00%)	50 (100.00%)	100 (100.00%)	
Pearson Chi-Square= 0.315a df= 2 statically not significant				
married status	group A	group B	Total	P value
unmarried	5 (10.00%)	8 (16.00%)	13 (13.00%)	0.277
married	45 (90.00%)	42 (84.00%)	87 (87.00%)	
Total	50 (100.00%)	50 (100.00%)	100 (100.00%)	
Fisher exact test = 0.796a df= 1 statically not significant				
parity	group A	group B	Total	P value
Nullipara	3(6%)	9(18%)	12(12%)	0.043*
Primipara	5 (10.00%)	8 (16.00%)	13 (13.00%)	
Para2	6 (12.00%)	12 (24.00%)	18 (18.00%)	
Para 3	13 (26.00%)	10 (20.00%)	23 (23.00%)	
Para 4	12 (24.00%)	8 (16.00%)	20 (20.00%)	
para 5	11 (22.00%)	3 (6.00%)	14 (14.00%)	
Total	50 (100.00%)	50 (100.00%)	100 (100.00%)	
Pearson Chi-Square = 11.255a df= 5 statically significant *				
Bleeding pattern	group A	group B	Total	P value
no	0 (0%)	50(100%)	50(50%)	0.001*
Menorrhagia	22(44%)	0	22(22%)	
Oligomenorrhoea	8(16%)	0	8(8%)	
Polymenorrhagia	11(22%)	0	11(11%)	
Metrorrhagia	9(18%)	0	9(9%)	
Total	50(100%)	50(100%)	100(100%)	
Pearson Chi-Square = 100.005a df= 4 statically significant *				

Figure 1: distribution of case group according bleeding pattern. N=50

In Table 2, the result of current study showed the relationship between T3, T4 and TSH testing with study groups. Where we note that 14% of patients have higher T3 and 12% have lower T3, while among group B only 6% of patients who have lower in T3 and no case of hight T3 and with statically differences (p =

0.010), with regard to the T4 test, the result revealed that 28% of patients in group A had lower T4 compared to group B were (10%) while 14% of patients in group A were having higher T4 opposite to no case (0), among group B with statistically significant association ($p = 0.001$). But in the TSH test, we see that more patients had higher level of TSH among group A than group B (54% and 10%, respectively) with significant differences ($p = 0.001$).

Table 2: distribution of study sample according thyroid test.

T3	group A	group B	total	P value
normal	37	47	84	0.010*
	74.00%	94.00%	84.00%	
low	6	3	9	
	12.00%	6.00%	9.00%	
high	7	0	7	
	14.00%	No case	7.00%	
total	50	50	100	
	100.00%	100.00%	100.00%	
Pearson Chi-Square = 9.190a df= 2 statically significant *				
T4	group A	group B	total	P value
normal	29	45	74	0.001*
	58.00%	90.00%	74.00%	
low	14	5	19	
	28.00%	10.00%	19.00%	
high	7	0	7	
	14.00%	No case	7.00%	
total	50	50	100	
	100.00%	100.00%	100.00%	
Pearson Chi-Square = 14.565a df= 4 statically significant *				
TSH	group A	group B	Total	P value
normal	16	45	61	0.001*
	32.00%	90.00%	61.00%	
low	7	0	7	
	14.00%	No case	7.00%	
high	27	5	32	
	54.00%	10.00%	32.00%	
total	50	50	100	
	100.00%	100.00%	100.00%	
Pearson Chi-Square = 35.911a df= 2 statically significant *				

In group A of the current study the results showed that 14% of patients had hyperthyroidism, 26% had subclinical hypothyroidism, and 32% had hypothyroidism compared to group B who found 12% had hypothyroidism and only 4% of them have subclinical hypothyroidism and no case of hyperthyroidism with statically significant association ($p=0.001$). as showed in table 3.

Table 3: distribution of study sample according thyroid dysfunction.

thyroid dysfunction	group A	group B	Total	P value
euthyroid	14	42	56	< 0.001*
	28.00%	84.00%	56.00%	
Hypothyroidism	16	6	22	
	32.00%	12.00%	22.00%	
subclinical hypothyroidism	13	2	15	
	26.00%	4.00%	15.00%	
Hyperthyroidism	7	0	7	
	14.00%	No case	7.00%	
Total	50	50	100	
	100.00%	100.00%	100.00%	
Pearson Chi-Square = 33.612a df= 4 statically significant *				

Regarding to correlation between thyroid dysfunction and bleeding pattern among group A , we see in result most women with menorrhagia were euthyroid (45%) and only 36% had hypothyroidism, while 50% of patients that have oligomenorrhoea associated hyperthyroidism. regarding to polymenorrhagia the result showed that 45% of patients with subclinical hypothyroidism and 27% patients with hypothyroidism, with statically significant association between bleeding pattern and thyroid function test (p=0.010). as shown in table 4 .

Table 4: association between Bleeding pattern and thyroid dysfunction.

Bleeding pattern	euthyroid	hypothyroid	subclinical hypothyroidism	Hyperthyroidism	Total	P value
Menorrhagia	10	8	2	2	22	0.010*
	45.50%	36.40%	9.10%	9.10%	100.00%	
Oligomenorrhoea	1	2	1	4	8	
	12.50%	25.00%	12.50%	50.00%	100.00%	
Polymenorrhagia	2	3	5	1	11	
	18.20%	27.30%	45.50%	9.10%	100.00%	
Metrorrhagia	1	3	5	0	9	
	11.10%	33.30%	55.60%	No case	100.00%	
Total	14	16	13	7	50	
	28.00%	32.00%	26.00%	14.00%	100.00%	
Pearson Chi-Square = 21.550a df= 9 statically significant *						

In present study, the result showed the distribution of prolactin level according to study group, we see more prevalence of hyperprolactinemia among group A than group B (58% and 14% respectively) with statically significant association (p=0.001). as shown in table 5.

Table 5. Association between study groups and prolactin level

prolactin level	group A	group B	Total	P value
normal prolactin	21	43	64	0.001*
	42.00%	86.00%	64.00%	
hyperprolactinemia	29	7	36	
	58.00%	14.00%	36.00%	
Total	50	50	100	
	100.00%	100.00%	100.00%	
Pearson Chi-Square =21.771 a df= 1 statically significant *				

In table 6, the result showed the correlation between prolactin level and bleeding pattern, 36.4% from cases with menorrhagia had hyperprolactinemia and 75% among oligomenorrhoea, 72.7% among patient with polymenorrhagia While 77.8% from the patients with metrorrhagia had hyperprolactinemia. With statically significant association ($p=0.045$).

Table 6. Association between AUB diagnosis and prolactin level

Bleeding pattern	normal prolactin	hyperprolactinemia	Total	P value	
Menorrhagia	14 63.60%	8 36.40%	22 100.00%	0.045*	
Oligomenorrhoea	2 25.00%	6 75.00%	8 100.00%		
Polymenorrhagia	3 27.30%	8 72.70%	11 100.00%		
Metrorrhagia	2 22.20%	7 77.80%	9 100.00%		
Total	21 42.00%	29 58.00%	50 100.00%		
Pearson Chi-Square =7.610 a					df= 3 statically significant *

DISCUSSION

In the current study, the most prevalent age category were (40-45 years) 36% follow by 22% incidence in the 35-40 years and with statically significant association between age and study groups ($p=0.021$). this result similar to Phukan JK et al. (5). reported the highest incidence in the > 40 years age group, which is 40% followed by 28.2% incidence in the 31 to 40 years age group. Sun Y. et al. (6). study found the prevalence rate in women aged 45 to 49 was 39.2% and in women aged 40 to 44 years was 36.9%. but in study conducted by Marie KJ. Et al. (7). Dysfunctional menstruation was more common among parous women than in nulliparous women. This was because of alterations in spiral arterioles of endometrium with age and parity, this is also according to Patel et al (8). In the present study showed the AUB more among patients with multiparous 50% of the patients were para 3 and 4. This agree with Krishnaveni MS. et al. (9). The Majority of patients were multiparous with parity more than 2 (50%), and 6% nulliparous. In the Pujari P, et al. (10). While Kazemijalish H. et al. (11). study found 45% of patient were more than para 2. The result of current study showed most prevalent types of bleeding pattern among group A were menorrhagia (44%), follow it polymenorrhagia (22%) and after that coming metrorrhagia (18%) and finally oligomenorrhoea (16%). This result similar to study conducted by Thakur M, et al. (12). In this study found the most common complaint was menorrhagia which was present in 40.5% of cases and the second most complaint was polymenorrhagia in (29.11%) patients which are followed by oligomenorrhoea in (15.1%) patients. Also This result was similar to a study carried out by Kaur et al.(13), Singh P et al. (53) and while the study conducted by Fakhar et al.(14). observed the menorrhagia were 45% followed by polymenorrhagia in 30% of cases. The result of current study showed the prevalence of thyroid dysfunction was 44% among study groups (7% of patients had hyperthyroidism, 15% had subclinical hypothyroidism, and 22% had hypothyroidism) with statically significant association ($p=0.001$). specifically, the prevalence of thyroid dysfunction among patients with AUB patients were 32% hypothyroidism, 26% subclinical hypothyroidism and 14% hyperthyroidism. This result agrees with study conducted Phukan JK et al. (15). That found 24% hypothyroidism of patients with AUB. In Byna P. et al. (16). Thyroid abnormality: Out of 55 women with AUB found (21.8%) were hypothyroid and (12.7%) were hyperthyroid. showed (22% hypo, 14% hyper, 64% euthyroid). Mukherjee & Gosh. et al (17). showed 44% incidence of hypothyroidism in their study. Doifode & Fernandes et al. (18). showed 28.17 % incidence of hypothyroidism in DUB patients and 12%

hyperthyroidism. Gowri et al. (18) that found hypothyroidism in 17.6% cases and subclinical hypothyroidism were 20%. On other hand the study by Barya S, et al. (19). showed 68% of the patients with AUB were euthyroid, 17% had subclinical hypothyroidism and 12% were diagnosed to be hypothyroid and 3% patients had hyperthyroidism. In patients presenting with menorrhagia, 76.08% were euthyroid, 15.21% had subclinical hypothyroidism and 8.69% were diagnosed as hypothyroids. In patients who presented with oligomenorrhoea, 38.88% were euthyroid, 27.77% had subclinical hypothyroidism and 22.22% had overt hypothyroidism and 11.11% were diagnosed as hyperthyroid. Patients presenting with polymenorrhoea, 22.22% had subclinical hypothyroidism and 11.11% had hypothyroidism. In our study the most women with menorrhagia were euthyroid (45%) and only 36% had hypothyroidism, while 50% of patients that have oligomenorrhoea associated hyperthyroidism. regarding to polymenorrhagia the result showed that 45% of patients with subclinical hypothyroidism and 27% patients with hypothyroidism, with statically significant association between bleeding pattern and thyroid function test ($p=0.010$). Other reports found euthyroid in 57.13% and 30% had hypothyroidism with menorrhagia and in the study by Rema V. Nair et al (20). While Oligomenorrhoea as the most common AUB patterns in Hyperthyroid patients is supported by studies conducted by Jinger et al. (21). and Somani et al.(22)who showed Oligomenorrhoea as 75% and 55.5% respectively. In Sudha HC, et al. (23)study, found the commonest menstrual abnormality seen in hypothyroidism was polymenorrhoea (25%), followed by polymenorrhagia (20%), while 11.4% had menorrhagia. Subclinical hypothyroidism was seen in 14% of cases with polymenorrhagia. In another study done by Kattel et al. (24).thyroid dysfunction was present in 20% of abnormal uterine bleeding cases out of which 19% had hypothyroidism and 1% had hyperthyroidism. In the present study hyperprolactinemia responsible for AUB was found in (58%) of patients included 75% among oligomenorrhoea While 77% from the patients with metrorrhagia. With statically significant association ($p=0.045$). this result agrees with Berinder et al.(25). in a study on 271 women with hyperprolactinemia (71% of whom had hyperprolactinemia) observed that 26% had oligomenorrhoea and 61% had amenorrhoea. ouraine et al. similarly observed in their cohort of 122 patients with hyperprolactinemia that around 66% patients had amenorrhoea and 26% oligomenorrhoea.(26).while in study conducted by Shin et al.(27). observed the prevalence of hyperprolactinemia is 20% in women with abnormal uterine bleeding with found positive correlation between TSH and Prolactin for AUB. In Muttappallymyalil J, et al. (28).found the prevalence of hyperprolactinemia is 15-20% in women with abnormal uterine bleeding, and High serum prolactin level was observed in 11.3% of the participants with oligomenorrhoea, 7.3% with polymenorrhoea, 3.7% with menometrorrhagia, 10.3% with menorrhagia, and 18.9% with inter-menstrual bleeding.

Conclusion

From our study it is evident that thyroid disorder and hyperprolactinemia is associated with abnormal uterine bleeding in a significant number of patients.

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